

Stress as a Predictor of Cognitive Functions among Medical Students

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Medical students are generally under considerable stress and pressure during their medical training, as they are required to understand as well as deal with complex medical concepts, practices, extended study hours, rigorous selection process, physical, emotional and financial strain. And, this elevated stress adversely affects their cognitive functioning, which often leads to poor decision-making, inadequate problem-solving, memory and attention-related problems. The higher-order cognitive processes, like working memory, cognitive flexibility and inhibitory control, play a vital role in learning, decision-making and overall academic performance. The present study aimed to identify the relationship between stress and cognitive functions among medical students. The study employed a correlational design. A hundred ($N=100$) medical students aged between 18-32 years were taken as samples for the current study. In the present study, Life Stress Scale constructed by Kumar (2002) was used to examine the levels of stress and BRIEF (Adult-A) developed by Roth, Isquith, and Gioia (2005) and Hindi version prepared by Yadav and Singh (2017) was used to measure cognitive functions among the participants. Correlational analysis showed that a significant positive relationship exists between stress and cognitive functions (executive functions). Medical students with high levels of stress reported poor executive functioning ($r = .636, p < 0.01$) across most of the domains of the behavioral regulation index ($r = .591, p < 0.01$) and metacognition index ($r = .595, p < 0.01$). The study contributes to the understanding of how stress impacts essential cognitive processes in high-pressure academic environments and emphasizes the need for institutional support to mitigate its effects.

Keywords: Medical students, stress, executive functions, behavioral regulation, metacognition, cognitive functions

Medical school is a highly demanding and intense experience which often challenges students in various ways. Extended periods of study, emotional stress and academic rigor can have an adverse impact on students' mental, emotional, and physical health. Medical students most often experience extended hours of study, the pressure of exams, and the emotional demands of patient care. Witnessing as well as dealing with life-and-death situations, human suffering, and

navigating ethical dilemmas might be overwhelming, especially for those early in their training (Goldstein & Shaulov, 2024).

Likewise, the transition from theory to practice can be difficult. Most of the students find it difficult to adapt to the fast-paced, high-pressure environment of clinical practice, which requires quick decision-making, and patients' lives rely on the knowledge and skills of the healthcare team. Over time, such high and consistent levels of stress among medical students might result in burnout, which is distinguished by elevated levels of emotional exhaustion (Khurshid et al., 2025). Stress might influence an individual's physical, social and emotional development (Lumen Learning n.d., 2026).

In addition to the stressful nature of undertaking a medical degree, medical students may experience more stress because of their financial status and personal relationships (Bugaj et al., 2016). A study conducted at a medical school in Thailand investigated the causes of stress and found that the major cause of stress experienced by the majority of the students related to academic activity, like assessment (99%), elevated workload (96.3%) and poor results (92.9%) (Saipanish, 2009). This demonstrates how stress can be induced by academic demands, but at the same time, stress can lead to poorer academic outputs, which consequently results in a vicious cycle of academic burden causing more stress, which results in decreased academic performance, which further results in stress and so on (Dyrbye et al., 2005). O'Rourke et al. (2010) demonstrated in their study that a large percentage of medical students suffer from anxiety disorders because increased levels of stress are closely associated with emotional as well as behavioral challenges. Heightened stress during medical school increases the risk of problems like difficulty managing interpersonal conflicts, sleep disorders, reduced concentration as well as attention, academic misconduct, depression, faulty judgment, increased chance of error,

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and unprofessional behavior, involving negligence (Khan et al., 2015). Medical students are more prone to high anxiety and perceived stress, which adversely impacts their physical and mental health and also interferes with their academic performance (Ebrahim et al., 2024).

A large number of studies demonstrate that stress has an adverse impact on the physical and psychological health of students. Stress affects the immune system (Caserta et al., 2008; Fagundes et al., 2013; Wyman et al., 2007) and consequently enhances the chance of an individual falling ill. Kuhlmann (2005) and Oei et al. (2007) have concluded on the basis of their study that chronic stress can impair memory by disturbing information encoding as well as retrieval processes. When the body is under stress, it discharges stress hormones into the blood as its natural response. The overproduction of cortisol (a stress hormone) has a catastrophic effect on memory. It has a specific effect on the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex, including the amygdala. Under normal circumstances, the hippocampus regulates cortisol production through the medium of a negative feedback loop because it incorporates several cortisol-sensitive receptors. Increased levels of cortisol hinder the hippocampus's capacity to encode and recover memories because of the persistent stress. Lupien et al. (2009) concluded on the basis of their study that stress has an intense impact on the human nervous system, consequently leading to structural changes in different areas of the brain. Chronic exposure to stress probably causes brain shrinkage and a decrease in brain weight (Sarahian et al., 2014). Such physiological variations in the brain are related to memory, cognitive function, and the way individuals react to stress (Lupien et al., 2009). Pascoe et al. (2019) found that the chronic stress related to university life hurts students' capacity for learning, academic performance, accomplishment of educational as well as vocational aspirations, sleep habits, and prevention of both physical and psychological health.

Sandi (2013) revealed that stress hurts cognition, depending on its kind, timing, intensity, and duration. It is globally accepted that a moderate level of stress enhances cognitive function improvement, especially verbal or verbatim memory. In spite of this, if stress exceeds a predefined threshold, which varies from individual to individual, it might lead to cognitive impairments, specifically in memory and judgment. The effects of stress on the prefrontal cortex and hippocampus can cause difficulties or impairments in memory and judgment (Sandi, 2013).

Empirical studies among medical students are scarce but suggestive. For instance, a recent study by Kumar et al. (2024) concludes that exam stress adversely impacts the cognitive performance of medical students. Another study by Sarkar et al. (2014) among first-year MBBS students reveals that stress is very common and it negatively affects the cognitive function of students. Mohamed et al. (2023) found in their study that perceived stress is highly correlated with executive dysfunction. Additionally, it has a significant impact on decision-making (Ajilchi & Nejati, 2017). Shields et al. (2016) revealed that stress reduces working memory, cognitive flexibility, and cognitive inhibition, but on the other hand, it increases response inhibition.

In this way, there is a theoretical as well as empirical justification and support for the hypothesis that increased levels of stress might be associated with poor cognitive (executive) functioning among medical students.

Rationale of the Study

Medical students encounter elevated levels of academic, clinical and emotional demands. It had been well-established that extended periods of stress adversely affect cognitive functions, specifically executive functions (working memory, cognitive flexibility, & inhibitory control). These are crucial for quick and effective decision-making, problem-solving, and maintaining academic performance. Therefore, it is necessary to understand how stress influences executive functions among medical students, because cognitive impairments not only affect learning outcomes but also future clinical competence and patient safety.

Despite the importance of this issue, very small numbers of studies have examined the direct relationship between stress and executive functions. Exploring this relationship can provide comprehensive information regarding cognitive vulnerabilities caused by stress. There is an alarming need to focus attention on healthcare professionals. The present study attempts to address this gap by recognizing how varying levels of stress affect the cognitive functions (executive functions) of medical students.

Objectives of the Study

In view of the gaps available in the review of literature following objectives have been formulated:

- To identify the level of stress and cognitive functions (executive functions) among medical students.
- To find out the gender differences in stress and cognitive functions among medical students.
- To assess the relationship between stress and cognitive functions among medical students.

Hypotheses of the Study

On the basis of literatures, the following hypotheses were formulated:

- *H1*. The level of stress and cognitive functions (executive functions) would differ among medical students.
- *H2*. There would be significant gender differences in stress and cognitive functions among medical students.
- *H3*. There would be a significant and positive correlation between stress and cognitive functions among medical students.

Method

Participants

The sample of 100 Medical students (MBBS), age ranging between 18 to 32 years ($M= 1.52$, $SD= 0.68$), 63 males and 37 females, belonging to different government medical colleges of Kanpur Nagar ($n= 100$) were selected for the present study. A convenient sampling method was adopted for the selection of participants. They were selected based on their accessibility and availability.

Measures

Life Stress Scale (Kumar, 2002). The scale comprises 26 items in Hindi and each item was presented on a four-point Likert scale, with responses ranging from *very much* (4) to *not at all* (1). The Cronbach Alpha of the scale has been reported as 0.91.

The Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function-Adult Version (BRIEF-A; Roth, Isquith, & Gioia, 2005). The Hindi-version of the scale was prepared by Yadav and Singh (2017). This scale measures

one of the most important dimensions of cognitive functions, i.e., executive functions. The scale involves 75 items with two broad dimensions of executive functions, namely, Behavioral regulation and Metacognition Index. The dimension of Behavioral regulation contains 4 sub-scales, involving Inhibit, Shift, Emotional control, and Self-monitor. The Metacognition Index consists of 5 sub-scales, including Initiate, Working Memory, Plan/Organize, Task Monitor, and organization of Materials. Higher scores on the scale represent weak executive functioning and vice-versa. The Cronbach Alpha of the scale was calculated to be 0.90.

Results

For the analysis of data, the SPSS version 20 was used. Mean, standard deviation, and t-test were calculated. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to analyze the relationship between stress (predictor variable) and cognitive functions (criterion variable). Hierarchical regression analysis was used in order to understand the relative contribution of predictor variables in the prediction of the criterion variable.

Table 1

Mean, Standard Deviation and t-ratio of Stress and Cognitive Functions among Medical Students

Variables	Males (N=63)		Females (N=37)		t-ratio
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	
Stress	45.03	11.47	46.83	11.87	-.750
Behavioral Regulation Index	44.42	8.37	47.64	8.11	-1.878
Metacognition Index	61.39	11.05	61.21	9.86	.082
Global Executive Functions (Behavioral Regulation + Metacognition)	105.82	18.28	108.86	16.70	-.828

Note. t-values are not-significant

Table-1 shows the mean scores of male and female medical students on stress, behavioral regulation index, metacognition index, and global executive functioning. For stress, the mean scores of male participants were found to be $M= 45.03$, $SD= 11.47$ and for female participants, it was found to be $M= 46.83$, $SD= 11.87$. The difference was not statistically significant ($t= -.750$, $p>.05$). The mean scores for behavioral regulation of male participants were found to be $M= 44.42$, $SD= 8.37$ and for female participants, it was $M= 47.64$, $SD= 8.11$. Results indicated that the difference was not statistically significant ($t= -1.878$, $p>.05$). Mean scores for the metacognition index of male participants were calculated to be $M= 61.39$, $SD= 11.05$ and for female participants, it was $M= 61.21$, $SD= 9.86$. Results

showed that the difference was not statistically significant ($t= .082$, $p>.05$). For global executive functions, the mean scores of male participants were calculated to be $M= 105.82$, $SD= 18.28$ and for female participants, it was $M= 108.86$, $SD= 16.70$. The findings showed that the difference was not statistically significant ($t= -.828$, $p>.05$).

Thus, Hypothesis-1 that level of stress and cognitive functions (executive functions) would differ among medical students, is supported. Whereas Hypothesis-2 that there would be significant gender differences in stress and executive functions among medical students, is not supported.

Table 2

Correlation between Stress and Behavioral Regulation among Medical Students

Predictor Variable	Criterion Variable (Behavioral Regulation)				
	Inhibit	Shift	Emotional Control	Self-Monitor	Overall Behavioral Regulation
Stress	.543**	.356**	.401**	.437**	.591**

Note. ** $p < 0.01$ level

Table-2 represents the correlation values between stress and four dimensions of behavioral regulation, namely inhibit ($r=.543$, $p<.001$), shift ($r=.356$, $p<.001$), emotional control ($r=.401$, $p<.001$), and self-monitor ($r=.437$, $p<.001$). The correlation for stress and overall behavioral regulation was calculated to be $.591$, $p<.001$. It

shows that there exists a significant positive relationship between stress and all dimensions of behavioral regulation. Thus, the obtained values signified that medical students with elevated levels of stress experience an increased amount of behavioral regulation difficulties.

Table 3

Correlation between Stress and Metacognition among Medical Students

Predictor Variable	Criterion Variable (Metacognition)						
	Initiate	Working Memory	Plan/Organize	Task Monitor	Organization of Materials	Overall Metacognition	Global Executive Functions (Behavioral Regulation + Metacognition)
Stress	.547**	.524**	.509**	.133	.401**	.595**	.636**

Note. ** $p < 0.01$ level

The results obtained through Pearson correlation coefficient for stress and dimensions of Metacognition are shown in Table- 3. It represents that there exists a significant positive relationship between stress and four out of five dimensions of metacognition, i.e., initiate ($r=.547, p<.001$), working memory ($r=.524, p<.001$), plan/organize ($r=.509, p<.001$) and organization of materials ($r=.401, p<.001$). In addition, it has been found that correlation for task-monitor was found to be weaker and non-significant (.133). The

correlation coefficient for stress and overall metacognition was calculated to be .595, $p<.001$ and global executive functions (behavioral regulation + metacognition) was found to be .636, $p<.001$. Since, the higher scores on the executive functions measure indicate poor executive functioning, so, the obtained results imply that increased levels of stress are associated with broader challenges of executive functions, including both behavioral regulation and metacognition.

Table 4

Summary of Hierarchical Regression Analysis for Stress as Predictor and Behavioral Regulation as Criterion among Medical Students

Demographic Variables	Criterion Variable (Behavioral Regulation)									
	Inhibit		Shift		Emotional Control		Self- Monitor		Overall Behavioral Regulation	
	Step-1	Step-2	Step-1	Step-2	Step-1	Step-2	Step-1	Step-2	Step-1	Step-2
Age	.059	.104	.003	.032	-.024	.007	.100	.136	.044	.092
Gender	.060	.022	.111	.087	.255	.228	.173	.143	.189	.148
	Predictor Variable (Stress)									
Overall R ²	.007	.550***	.012	.352***	.066	.384***	.038	.438***	.037	.588***
R ² Change	.007	.299	.012	.122	.066	.146	.038	.189	.037	.341
F Change	.325	41.266***	.606	13.569***	3.444	17.749***	1.903	23.534***	1.845	52.631***
F	.325	14.062***	.606	4.979**	3.444	8.609***	1.903	9.408***	1.845	19.429***

Note. *** $p<.001$, ** $p<.01$, df1 and 2 (step-1) - 2, 97, df1 and 2 (step-2) - 3, 96

Table-4 demonstrates that stress accounted for 29.9% of variance in the explanation of inhibit (R^2 change= .299, F change= 41.266, $F=$ 14.062, $p<.001$), 12.2% variance in shift (R^2 change= .122, F change= 13.569, $F=$ 4.979, $p<.001$), 14.6% variance in emotional control (R^2 change= .146, F change= 17.749, $F=$ 8.609, $p<.001$), 18.9% variance in self-monitor (R^2 change= .189, F change= 23.534, $F=$ 9.408, $p<.001$) and 34.1% variance in overall behavioral

regulation (R^2 change= .341, F change= 52.631, $F=$ 19.429, $p<.001$) over and above the demographic variables. Altogether, the outcomes indicated that stress significantly and positively predicted all dimensions of behavioral regulation, i.e., inhibit ($R^2=$.550, $p<.001$), shift ($R^2=$.352, $p<.001$), emotional control ($R^2=$.384, $p<.001$), self-monitor ($R^2=$.438, $p<.001$), and overall behavioral regulation ($R^2=$.588, $p<.001$).

Table 5

Summary of Hierarchical Regression Analysis for Stress as Predictor and Metacognition as Criterion among Medical Students

Demographic Variables	Criterion Variable (Metacognition)											
	Initiate		Working Memory		Plan/ Organize		Task Monitor		Organization of Materials		Overall Metacognition	
	Step-1	Step-2	Step-1	Step-2	Step-1	Step-2	Step-1	Step-2	Step-1	Step-2	Step-1	Step-2
Age	.033	.079	.160	.023	-.069	-.027	.235	.248	.064	.098	.081	.131
Gender	.608	-.091	.110	.072	.011	-.025	.031	.020	-.093	-.122	-.003	-.046
	Predictor (Stress)											
Overall R ²	.004	.560***	.035	.536***	.005	.508***	.055	.153	.013	.419***	.007	.610***
R ² Change	.004	.310	.035	.284	.005	.255	.055	.023	.013	.173	.007	.368
F Change	.198	43.441***	1.770	40.086***	.239	33.117***	2.840	2.414	.661	20.419***	.325	56.381***
F	.198	14.670***	1.770	15.017***	.239	11.251***	2.840	2.726	.661	7.335***	.325	19.134***

Note. *** $p<.001$, df1 and 2 (step-1) 2, 97, df1 and 2 (step-2) - 3, 96

Table 5 shows that stress accounted for 31.0% variance in initiate (R^2 change= .310, F change= 43.441, $F=$ 14.670, $p<.001$), 28.4%

variance in working memory (R^2 change= .284, F change= 40.086, $F=$ 15.017, $p<.001$) and 25.5% variance in plan/organize (R^2

change= .255, F change= 33.117, F = 11.251, p <.001), 2.3% variance in task monitor (R^2 change= .023, F change= 2.414, F = 2.726, p <.05), 17.3% variance in organization of materials (R^2 change= .173, F change= 20.419, F = 7.335, p <.001), 36.8% variance in overall metacognition (R^2 change= .368, F change= 56.381, F = 19.134, p <.001) over and above the demographic variable.

Altogether, the obtained results indicated that stress positively and significantly predicted difficulties related to initiate (R^2 = .560, p <.001), working memory (R^2 = .536, p <.001), plan/organize (R^2 = .508, p <.001), task monitor (R^2 = .153, p >.05) organization of materials (R^2 = .419, p <.001), and overall metacognition (R^2 = .610, p <.001).

Table 6

Summary of Hierarchical Regression Analysis for Stress as Predictor and Global Executive Functions as Criterion among Medical Students

Demographic Variables	Criterion Variable (Global Executive Functions)					
	Behavioral Regulation		Metacognition		Global Executive Functions	
	Step-1	Step-2	Step-1	Step-2	Step-1	Step-2
Age	.044	.092	.081	.131	.069	.122
Gender	.189	.148	-.003	-.046	.088	.043
	Predictor Variable (Stress)					
		.588***		.610***		.643***
Overall R^2	.037	.378	.007	.374	.012	.420
R^2 Change	.037	.341	.007	.368	.012	.409
F Change	1.845	52.631***	.325	56.381***	.577	67.659***
F	1.845	19.429***	.325	19.134***	.577	23.202***

Note. *** p <.001, df 1 and 2 (step-1) - 2, 97, df 1 and 2 (step-2) - 3, 96

Table 6 shows that stress explained 34.1% variance in behavioral regulation (R^2 change= .341, F change= 52.631, F = 19.429, p <.001), 36.8% variance in metacognition (R^2 change= .368, F change= 56.381, F = 19.134, p <.001), and 40.9% variance in global executive functions (R^2 change= .409, F change= 67.659, F = 23.202, p <.001). Overall, the results indicated that stress significantly and positively predicted behavioral regulation (R^2 = .588, p <.001), metacognition (R^2 = .610, p <.001) and global executive functions (R^2 = .643, p <.001).

Discussion

The present study examined the relationship between stress and cognitive functions (executive functions) among medical students. Hypotheses 1 and 3 were accepted. Hypothesis 2 was rejected. The correlational analysis shows that stress has a positive and significant relationship with executive functions (cognitive functions), indicating that elevated levels of stress lead to poor executive functioning.

The first hypothesis stated that medical students would differ in levels of stress and executive functions (including all domains of the behavioral regulation index & metacognition index). And, it has been found that the scores obtained by students on stress and executive functions (cognitive functions) differ, but the variation is not very wide. The reason behind this might be the homogeneity of the sample, as medical students usually witness similar academic backgrounds, cognitive abilities, as well as training environments. They are most often exposed to comparable academic demands and stressors; their experiences, along with coping patterns, are likely to be similar, resulting in limited differences in scores. Also, medical training often promotes adaptive strategies like time management as well as flexibility, which can further reduce variation among students. Cultural or institutional factors, including structured

curriculum and supportive peer networks, might also contribute to more similar responses. The findings of the present study are supported by numerous studies. Łoś et al. (2020) concluded on the basis of their study that levels of stress differ within medical students and are meaningfully related to executive functioning. Hanafi et al. (2024) reported that the levels of stress change over time (severe stress increased over clinical years for most of the forms of stress). However, some studies show contradictory findings. Sorout et al. (2020) found no significant differences in mean scores of DASS, PSS, or P300, which clearly suggests that in the context of some “academic stress”, cognitive or executive-related functions may not necessarily decline, or at least, not in a simple linear way.

The second hypothesis was that there would be significant gender differences in stress and executive functions (cognitive functions) among medical students. The results revealed that no significant gender difference exists in stress and executive functions (cognitive functions). This absence of significant gender differences might be because of the fact that medical school admits a high-level cohort in which the cognitive abilities as well as resilience of all genders are equally strong. Both male and female students undergo similar academic workloads, clinical pressures and evaluation systems, which standardize exposure to stress. Furthermore, multiple studies demonstrate that gender differences in executive functions in the general population are relatively small and usually task-specific. Shared coping skills taught in medical school can further reduce variation. Consequently, any possible gender-based differences become minimal as well as statistically insignificant. These findings are inconsistent with Grissom and Reyes (2018) which suggests that there is little evidence for significant sex/gender variations in executive functions. There are no overall significant gender differences in any of the three domains of executive functions, including set-shifting, performance monitoring and response

inhibition (Gaillard et al., 2021). Another study by Upadhayay and Guragain (2014) found no strong or consistent gender differences in executive functions among medical students. Apart from this, numerous studies report contradictory findings. Apart from this, some researchers have found contradictory results. It has been concluded that under stress, both men and women exhibit distinct patterns of cerebral blood flow: men experience greater activation in the right prefrontal cortex, whereas women activate more limbic regions (Wang et al., 2007). Men showed a higher cortisol response; however, women remembered more positive as well as neutral terms. This gender difference illustrates how stress hormones affect memory and attention (Dumont et al., 2020).

The next hypothesis stated that a positive and significant relationship exists between stress and executive functions. The findings of the present study support this hypothesis. Since higher scores on the executive functions scale indicate poor executive (cognitive) functioning, this suggests that medical students with elevated levels of stress often exhibit poor executive functioning. Studies often find a positive relationship between stress and executive functions among medical students because high levels of stress results in increased cortisol levels, which suppresses the functioning of the prefrontal cortex. It weakens various essential cognitive processes like attention, planning, decision making, and working memory. Stress most often increases cognitive load, anxiety, and sleep problems. And all these difficulties lead to impaired executive functioning. All such biological as well as psychological factors contribute towards poor executive (cognitive) functioning among medical students. Similar results have been found by various other studies. It has been reported that medical students who experience anxiety/depression show deficits in executive functioning, which adversely affects their academic performance (Alfakeh et al., 2022 & Abdulghani et al., 2011). A large number of studies conclude that acute levels of stress reduce “core” executive functioning, specifically working memory, cognitive flexibility, and inhibition (Shields et al. 2016; Girotti et al., 2017). Sarkar et al. (2023) found a weak correlation between stress and cognitive functions. But some studies report contradictory findings. Möschl et al. (2022) found no significant correlation in chronic stress with the latent “general executive functions” factor. Albaladejo-González et al. (2024) suggested that in some cases, stress is not a predictor of executive functions.

Furthermore, the correlation of stress with all domains of executive functions was also analyzed. The findings reveal that higher levels of stress lead to poorer inhibitory control, difficulty in shifting tasks, more emotional deregulation, weak self-monitoring, increased difficulty in initiating tasks, poor working memory and organization skills, along with decreased planning and organizing abilities. The highest impact of stress has been seen on initiation, inhibition, working memory and planning. Whereas, no significant impact of stress was witnessed on task-monitoring abilities.

Limitations and Future Suggestions

The present study has several limitations. The participants were selected from medical colleges of Kanpur city, which makes it difficult to generalize the findings to the wider populations. This study used self-report measures for both stress and executive functions, which can increase subjective bias. The study employs a cross-sectional design, which prevents the formation of causal

relationships between these variables. The present study provides a significant and relevant contribution to the available literature, but further research is required to delve deeper into this specific direction. Regardless of all the limitations, this study has several crucial implications. The significant impact of stress on different domains and dimensions of executive functions highlights the alarming need for medical institutions and policy-makers to incorporate interventions related to stress-management programs, mental health counseling, as well as cognitive skill development into their curriculum. The obtained results of this study emphasize the importance of enhancing emotional well-being and resilience among medical students, so that improvements in stress management can boost academic performance, clinical decision-making and overall psychological health. More studies with large and diverse samples with longitudinal designs are encouraged in order to extend and strengthen these findings.

Implications of the Study

The findings of the present study reveal that there is a high need to prioritize mental-health support along with students' well-being in medical colleges. Incorporating effective stress management programs, resilience building sessions, as well as mindfulness trainings can help medical students in enhancing their cognitive flexibility, self-regulation skills, planning and decision making. Institutions can implement policies that necessarily talk about eliminating academic burdens or strains, improving mentoring systems and also building supportive peer networks in order to reduce stress levels. Conducting psychological screenings and providing counseling services at regular intervals can help recognize students dealing with high levels of stress or cognitive impairments at an early stage. Altogether, this study suggests that promoting well-being is not essential for academic success of students, but also for making competent, emotionally balanced and cognitive skilled future healthcare professionals.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the present study, it can be concluded that stress plays a significant as well as detrimental role in the executive functioning of medical students. These cognitive abilities are crucial for effective learning, problem-solving, quick decision-making, and professional competence in the medical field. The obtained results highlight the urgent need for medical institutions as well as policy-makers to identify stress as a notable factor affecting cognitive functions, performance and overall well-being. By integrating mental health support, stress reduction techniques, and cognitive skill- enhancement programs into medical training, institutions can nurture healthier, stronger, and better-performing healthcare professionals of the future.

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